

Manure and soil health in mountainous regions: needs from an economic, policy and social perspective

Based on the [EU definition](#), “**Manure** (also known as **livestock manure**) is organic matter, mostly derived from animal faeces and urine, but normally also containing plant material (often straw), which has been used as bedding for animals and has absorbed the faeces and urine”. The management of manure in mountainous systems is shaped not only by biophysical conditions but also by economic viability, policy frameworks, and social dynamics.

Needs from an economic, policy and social perspective

Figure 1 Manure gathered to be applied in a small mountainous farm of Evrytania (Photo: A. Pantera)

Traditionally and in the past, farmers did not need to use chemical fertilizers and covered most of their soil amendment needs with manure.

At the same time, croplands served as major outlets for the manure produced in livestock farms, strengthening synergies among crop farmers and livestock breeders. On a broader scale, high transportation costs, limited infrastructure, small farm sizes, and seasonal accessibility constraints restrict the efficient collection, storage, and application of manure in more distant areas. Although the manure utilization can reduce dependence on inorganic fertilizers and enhance soil resilience, investments in manure infrastructures and processing technologies often exceed the financial capacity of small-scale producers. Therefore, appropriate incentives and cooperative schemes are required to strengthen the local circular nutrient economy. At policy level, regulations concerning water protection, erosion control, and the reduction of greenhouse gas emissions must be adapted to the specific characteristics of mountainous terrain, where the risks of runoff and nutrient losses from manure are higher than in plain areas. At social level, the aging rural population, labour shortages, and changes in land use affect management practices and the maintenance of soil fertility.

ADDITIONAL INFORMATION

Advancing manure-based soil health strategies in mountainous regions require a multidimensional approach that aligns economic incentives, context-sensitive policies, and socially embedded practices to ensure environmental sustainability and rural resilience. The combination of traditional practices with scientific innovation can enhance adaptability and long-term resilience.

KEYWORDS

Soil amendments, rangelands, soil fertility conservation, social resilience, circular nutrient economy

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